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**Community Development Projects In
Tuti Island: The Case of Tuti
Development Company.**

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Dedication

To my parents and my beloved

“Tuti Island”

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Chapter One

Introduction

Chapter One

1:1 Introduction:

The term Community Development is nowadays widely known and with its concern with socio-economic development of local communities. As a field of research community development is receiving increasing attention from all kinds of academic disciplines economics, geography, anthropology ... etc.

The term community development is not a new one - as we will see later – but its principles were – in fact – applied long before anyone had thought of such a term. It is only the emphasis that is new, rather than the principles.

Community development projects or programs are planned to play an important role in the development of local communities both socially and economically. These programs may lead to radical changes in the local communities, and since community development programs depend primarily on local initiatives, they tend to activate community participation. In short, community development programs in long run encourage people to become more self-reliant in all social, economic and cultural aspects, and be more participative in improving their communities.

However, Tuti Development Company is one of the community development projects in the Island, it was established in 1946 to roll up the development wheel to its peak. Since then, it has been involved in different types of communal activities.

At that early time, the people of Tuti were faced by a critical situation when the colonial authorities had tried to expropriate the entire Island and resettle its residents elsewhere. So in order to stop this, Tuti people insisted on establishing a development project on the Island to counter the colonial authorities' claim, that the Island's resources were not

fully utilized. So once the company was established, it immediately started the development processes in the Island, and it achieved a lot for the residents.

1:2 Objectives of the study:

As far as this study is concerned, the major objectives pursuit are:

1. To trace the establishment and the objectives of Tuti development company.
2. To assess the impact of the company on Tuti community, and to show to what extent that the stated objectives were realized.
3. To have a comprehensive evaluation for the company's performance.
4. To identify the main problems and the alternatives which were adopted, and finally.
5. To assess the future prospects of the company.

1:3 Literature review:

Arabi (1979) wrote a thesis on community development in the Sudan. She undertook a review of the role of the community development in the process of nation building. In addition, she put emphasis on the approaches, and the methodologies as applied in the third world. Arabi (1979) stated that community development programs usually encompasses-

- (i) Adult literacy and basic social education.
- (ii) Work among women and young people.
- (iii) Low-level extension education.
- (iv) Self-help construction projects.
- (v) The stimulation of cooperation and the small-scale industries.

Moreover, Arabi (1979) discussed the structure of polices and administration within the community development field. In addition, a

marked stress on popular participation was put, as it effects development within the community.

In reviewing the Sudan experience in the community development field, she stated that community development in the Sudan started as a movement of mass education, which was related to the adult education since earlier times (adult education started in 1944). She traced up the history of the community development in the Sudan, giving its history in the ministry of the local government, and later in the social affairs ministry by the introduction of the decentralization. Furthermore, Arabi (1979) evaluated the Khartoum North project of 1963, which supported and financed by the United Nations. This pilot project began with 28 villages with population about 30,000 persons and later it expanded to about 44 villages. The pilot project included the following fields: agriculture, health, education, cooperation, vocational training and work among women.⁽¹⁾

About Tuti Island on the other hand, there is a reasonably good deal of researches carried on Tuti and its population. Hassan (1963) wrote a dissertation under the little "agriculture in the Island.

He provided a historical account of agriculture in the Island, types of crops that were grown in the Island since earlier times, and that included, slightly, Tuti Development Company and its objectives. Besides, he also described the social life with some consideration e.g. education, and population.⁽¹⁾

⁽¹⁾ Hassan, Omer B. agriculture in Tuti Island. Unpublished B. A. Dissertation 1963.

⁽¹⁾ Arabi, Safia M. Community development in the Sudan M.Sc. thesis 1979.

Especially in the fields of education, settlements, and health services. That was motivated by the small size of the Island and the growing population. ⁽²⁾

1:4 Research Methodology:

In the process of doing this research, various types of information were required, for example, information about community development concept, information about Tuti Island, in general, and information about Tuti development company and its establishment, objectives and performance.

So to realize these types of information a various methodologies were followed, in this study I have relied heavy on interviews, secondly information from the available literature, and observation was used here. However, the major methodology, which was used – interviews –, has two types, first the interviews with the company staff, which included members of the Board of Directors, workers, which need not to be sampled. Second, were the interviews with farmers dealing with the company? These farmers' interviews were based primarily on the stratified random sample.

The sample size was planned to constitute 10% of all farms that belong to the company – the study area -, since the total number of these farms is 182 farms, the sample size was 18 farms.

1:5 Problems of the study:

No doubt, I faced many problems, such as the lack of written data about Tuti Development Company. So nearly all of the collected data was obtained through interviews. In addition, I did not find any farmer with any regular records about his production, income, or expenditure. Therefore, it was difficult for me to provide this study with the enough statistical

⁽²⁾Abdul El-Raheem, Izz El-din Ahmed, Future problems in Tuti Island, 1975 Geography (B.A) general (typed).

illustrations. Even the company itself has a very bad and primitive method of documentation and old keeping system, and as a result, most of its early documents were lost and destroyed.

Chapter Two

Community Development

Chapter Two

2:1 Emergence of the Community

Development Concept

Some scholars believe that the term community Development is an old one. Dunham states that [the term community development is not new].

As far back as 1915, a book dealing primarily with economic aspects of community was published under the title:-

Community Development Making the small town a better place to live. The term community development (though not of course in its contemporary technical sense) is found also in Jesse F. steiner's 1928 volume of case studies, the American community in action (in chapter with the title "social change and community development")⁽¹⁾.

Batten provides us with more detailed statement on this issue [Enthusiasts for community development sometimes speak about it or write about it as if it was something entirely new, and they irritate the people who feel that community development is not new, but that its principles were – in fact applied by a multitude of individual government officers and missionaries long before anyone thought of such a term as community development.

So community development as we recognize it today is based on, and has growth out of, experience of the past. What is new is that these principles are becoming more widely recognized than ever before, and more purposefully applied by many agencies which are basing their polices upon them, it is the emphasis that is new, rather than the principles.]⁽¹⁾

⁽¹⁾ Dunham, Arther (1972).

⁽¹⁾ Ibid ..

on the other hand, we find another group of scholars who deal with community development as a new concept e.g. sanders says [the term community development is a brainchild of our generation].⁽²⁾

However, Abdul Atti gives us a more precise detail when he states [the beginning of what is now known as community development can be traced back to the 1940's when the government of India set up relief camps for West Pakistani refugees.] by Sanders (1958) as cited by Abdul Atti ⁽³⁾

However, we can state that, community development concept is a new and on old one, it is old in the sense that throughout the human history many community development activities have been undertaken by the communities itself, with regardless to its contemporary meanings. But community development with its current and technical sense with its multidimensional scope is a recent social invention which used for large scale social planning / development.

2:2 Essence and Objectives:

The term community development is often misunderstood and wrongly applied by who call for it and those who practice it. This is so because the term itself is elusive and open. So it was sometimes found difficult to form a precise definition of the term, and as sanders says. (I shall not try to give a precise narrowly restricted definition of community development, but I prefer to let it mean whatever its promoters want it to mean).⁽¹⁾ Vasso takes this further when he says that (Community Development is open to many subjective interpretations by those involved

⁽²⁾ Batten, T. R. (n.d).

⁽³⁾ Sanders, Irwin T. (1958).

⁽¹⁾ Durham, Arther (1972).

directly or indirectly in community development whether they are community workers, politicians, social workers, agencies, administration, or local leaders).⁽²⁾

Dunham emphasizes this when he states that (in north America, the term community development is used today, loosely, ambiguously and with variety of meanings, some of them directly conflicting).⁽³⁾

Notwithstanding all the above views there are several attempts which were done to define the term community development. The United Nations seminar on community development and social welfare in urban areas, in Geneva 1956 adopted a definition of community development which connotes:-

- 1- The term community development has become into international use age to connote the process by which the efforts of people themselves are united with those of governmental authorities to improve the economic, social, and cultural conditions of the community, to integrate these communities into the life of the national, and enable them to contribute fully to national progress.
- 2- This complex of process is then made up of two essential elements: the participation by the people themselves in the efforts to improve their level of living with as much reliance as possible on their own initiatives; and the provision of technical and other services in ways which encourage initiatives, self-help and mutual-help. To make these more effective the qualifications are first technical assistance must be provided by voluntary (this is non-governmental) organizations as well as by governmental

⁽²⁾ Batten, T. R. (n.d).

⁽³⁾ Sanders, Irwin T. (1958).

agencies, and second, in some cases the people of the community themselves may initiate and carry on a community development program or activities without significant technical assistance).⁽¹⁾

In 1948 the Cambridge summer conference on African Administration gives the following definition for community development (a movement designed to promote better living for the whole community, with the active participation, if possible on the initiative of the community, but if this initiative is not forthcoming spontaneously, by the use of techniques for arousing and stimulating it in order to secure its active and enthusiastic response to the movement, and community development must make use of the closest association with local government bodies).⁽²⁾

A More explicit definition for community development was introduced in 1953 by Goswami and Roy for whom community development projects aim at:-

- 1- Introducing changes and undertaken works in villages which will lead to the economic, social and cultural improvement of the life of the villagers.
- 2- Inducing the villagers to carry out by themselves as many of the work as possible.
- 3- Securing complete co-operation between the government agencies and the villagers in this effort)⁽¹⁾.

The objectives of the community development was summarized as the following: (to induce social change for balance human and material betterment to strength the institutional structure in such a way as to

⁽¹⁾ Dunham, Arther (1972).

⁽²⁾ Batten, T. R. (n.d).

⁽¹⁾ Dunham, Arther (1972).

facilitate social change and the process of growth; to ensure the fullest possible participation in development process and to promote social justice by permitting less privileged groups to give expression to their aspirations and to participate in development activities)⁽²⁾.

More recently the workshop on "future direction of assistance to refugees in Sudan, sponsored by UNHCR and CFR in Khartoum 1986, adopted the following definition of community development:

- To develop community welfare as regards social, and economic basic needs {health, education, water ... etc.} as well as productive activities.
- To foster participation in the development of the community.
- External input is need, community development agents, officers, who should ensure that these change are developing smoothly and don't create conflicts and incoherences between the 'existent projects' and 'proposed projects' which might definitely endanger the success of the project.⁽³⁾

However, there is a considerable agreement upon some aspects in the community development processes, that most of what was said above stress highly on the community participation, social, cultural and economic improvements in the communities, and finally the integration of the community development projects.

Community participation is widely regarded as the mainspring of community development process. Community participation in community development project refers according to Abdul Atti – to the active involvement of the population in decision – making, implementation,

⁽²⁾ Batten, T. R. (n.d).

⁽³⁾ Sanders, Irwin T. (1958).

benefits and evaluation at all stages of the project cycle. This is sometimes referred to as self-help [see fig. No. (1)]

Fig. (1) Four kinds of participation

As far as the economic, social and cultural improvement are concerned, it is important to avoid the inequality in the benefits, and here Abdul Atti thinks that, the way out can possibly be through the identification of specific target group for a particular project. For example, a program directed at increasing agricultural productivity may primarily benefit the rich land owners may benefit from a project in the field of non-agricultural employment creation. But this again raises the difficulty of selecting the target groups. So according to Abdul Atti, it must be remembered that the equality is not a substitute for economic growth. Thus, the development effort must include measures to reduce imbalances but should not be confined to them. Furthermore, from the experience the selection of some specific target groups is proved to be essential for C.D. program, and for integral rural development in general.

Community development programs are not implemented in isolation, but must be an integrate part of the national development effort. Also these community development programs can help in construct school, health centers, community centers, housing, roads, ... etc. Through the mobilization of voluntary labour and material contributions.⁽¹⁾

Form what was stated above it seems that, we can say that:

- (a) Community development is a process, which with its well defined steps and phases, leads to sequential changes that lead the community to pass from the simple life to a more advanced one;

⁽³⁾ Sanders, Irwin T. (1958).

⁽¹⁾ Dunham, Arther (1972).

- (b) Community development depends highly on the local initiatives, and local participation;
- (c) It should in the long run encourage people to become more self-reliant in their local communities by improving the available physical and human resources.

2:3 Phases in Community Development:

Community development process involves certain successive and related steps that end up with the stated and planned objectives. Taylor, for example, identifies steps in the community development process:

First, the systematic discussion of common felt needs by community members.

Second, systematic planning to carry out the first self-help undertaking selected by community.

Third, the almost complete mobilization and harnessing of the physical, economic and social potentialities of the community.

Fourth, creation of the aspiration and determination to undertake additional community development projects.⁽¹⁾

50 Taylor believes that, community development process is over only when the fourth step is completed.

Hays pushes the matter further and states more detailed steps, as he identifies ten steps for the community development processes. Firstly, the consciousness of the need, some individuals or group becomes aware of the need. Secondly, spreading the consciousness, of the need, the leader convince his community of the reality of the need. Thirdly, projection of

Dunham, Arther (1972). ⁽¹⁾

the consciousness, the concerned group arouses wider interest. Fourthly, the emotional impulses to meet the need quickly. Fifthly, presentation of other solutions. Sixthly, conflict of solutions. Seventhly, investigation when expert assistance is often used. Eighthly, open discussion to the issue. Ninthly, integration of solutions and, tenthly, compromise on the basis of tentative progress.⁽²⁾

So all these steps are considered as the major steps to be followed successively in any community development program.

2: 4 Community Development in Tuti Island:

There are several community development activities carried out in Tuti Island. There are also certain factors which make the community development the most suitable approach for the Island's socio-economic advancement. Tuti is characterized by a unique unity, that all Islanders can be considered as a one large family, as they are dependents of the same grandfather. This means that the social structure is very homogeneous. Moreover this strong unity of the population was enhanced by certain historical events, most important was what is known as Tuti incident of 1944, Nile floods of 1946, 1975 and 1988. The nature of Tuti as an Island also played a major role in enhancing this unity among the Islanders. Furthermore; the high level of education among the Islanders. Which means a high level of awareness among them. Finally such a community with its unity, of the same grandfather. This means that the social structure is very homogeneous. Moreover this strong unity of the population was enhanced by certain historical events, most important was what is known

⁽²⁾ Batten, T. R. (1958).

as Tuti incident of 1944^{*}, Nile floods of 1946, 1975 and 1988. The nature of Tuti as an Island also played a major role in enhancing this unity among the Islanders. Furthermore; the high level of education among the Islanders. Which means a high level of awareness among them. Finally such a community with its unity, its relative isolation from the surrounding areas has more ability to create its own local leadership and social organization. So all these factors combined together to create an atmosphere suitable for the community development activities. In what follows some examples of the community development activities in the Island are provided.

2:4:1 Kora marriage system:

The Kora marriage system is an agreement made by heads of the families, to minimize the expenditure which usually spent on the wedding ceremonies. Sometime, it happens that a number of weddings take place at one calibration.

The essence of the Kora system is to solve the financial obstacles which face the youth and prevent them from getting married. However it is said that, the Kora system was originated in Tuti Island about one hundred years ago, and from there it spread outside the Island to other communities such as el-Geriaf.

In the past the Kora was the predominant system, so, that no one dared to break the system. Hassan stated that in 1963 65% of the population were got married.

In contrast, during 1970's the Kora predominance reduced, but since people in Tuti believe that Kora system can play a major to role in their

^{*} See chapter (4) historical background.

social life, a new committee was chosen in 1986 to resuscitate the Kora and look after it.

2: 4: 2 The Benevolent Societies:

There are two benevolent societies in Tuti Island, one in the northern part of the Island and another in the southern part. In the past when any somebody dies the bereaved family had to buy all the required equipment for serving the people who come to participate in the funeral. In order to serve the entire community, the benevolent societies were established primarily to provide the bereaved family with all its needs for the funeral. Its property contains cups, rugs, tents, chairs, electric lamps ... etc. each society has its general assembly, which meets regularly, and its function is to elect the committee which runs the society affairs, and collects the contributions from each family.

2: 4: 3 El-Nafier

It is one of the most important systems of the traditional activities among the Tuti community. According to this system, a group of people joint to gather to perform certain economic activities.

House building is the most dominant type for which el-Nafier is called. When the house is extremely old or when it fall down and the family has not the ability to pay, a person calls for el-Nafier.

However, the effect of this activity is clearly revealed during the last year following a heavy rainfall and floods of 1988, when a large number of houses fell down, and most of these houses were rebuilt though el-Nafier system.

Foot Note

- (1) Dunham, Arther, C. D in N. America, C. D journal vol. 7 No. 1, 1972.
- (2) Batten, T. R., communities and their development. London O.U.P pp. 2-3.
- (3) Sanders, Irwin T., The community. New York, the Ronald press Co. 1958 pp. 389-391.
- (4) Abdul Atti, Hassan A., Rural Development planning, 1988, U of K.
- (5) Sanders, Irwin T., theories of C.D.
- (6) Vasoo, S., Reviewing the directions of C.D. in Singapore, C.D. Journal vol. 19 No. (1), 1984.
- (7) Dunham, Arther, ibid.
- (8) Report of the U.N. Seminar on C.D. and social welfare in Urban areas, Geneva 1959 p.5.
- (9) C. D. A handbook.
- (10) Abdul Atti, Hassan A., ibid.
- (11) United Nations, E 71 IV. 2 "popular participation in development" chapter (1).
- (12) Report of workshop on future directions of assistance to refugees in Eastern Sudan, UNHCR & CFR Khartoum 1986.
- (13) Abdul Atti, Hassan A. ibid.
- (14) Taylor, Carl C., C.D. programs and methods C.D journal vol. 3, 1956.
- (15) Hays, Wayland J., The small community looks ahead, Newyork, Harcourt Brace and Co. 1947.

Chapter Three

Tuti Island: A Geographical Description

Chapter Three

3: 1 Site & Location of Tuti Island

Tuti Island is a crescent – shaped Island, it is in the heart of the three towns, Khartoum locates at the southern side of the Island, Omdurman at the western side and while Khartoum North at the Eastern side. [Map No. (1)]. It is completely surrounded by the water in the sense that, the White Nile flows on its Western side, and the Blue Nile surrounds it from south and east and one of its branches flows on its southern side to meet the White Nile at El-Mugran, the Nile flows northwards until it joins the second branch of the Blue Nile, which flows by the Eastern side of the Island, at the northern end of Tuti Island.

The river erosion has a serious effect on the Island's shape. For example, in the past the eastern bank of the Island was building into the river in a convex shape, but as a result of the river erosion it became has turned into a concave shape, as "Haddam activity" lateral erosion is very intensive here, due to the deflection of the current towards the Island's bank.

It is well known that the Tuti Island has been formed as a result of the silt depositions lies on sedimentary rocks – Nubian sand stone – at a depth of 5.30 foots. It is believed that these sedimentary rocks were originally a part of the "Karrari Hills"⁽¹⁾.

Tuti Island Site Location

Map No. (1)

⁽¹⁾

3: 2 Relief and drainage:

Tuti Island is formed over a sedimentary rocks, which are covered by clays and silt, these rocks outcrop in the central parts of the Island.

As far as relief is concerned, we can easily-identify that, according to the Tuti's contour map, the altitude is ranging between 75.68 to 78.15 fouts above sea level. The map shows that the highest area is the central parts 78.75 fouts, and then the altitude fluctuates between 76.25 to 77.60 fouts, but it is clear that the lowest area is the south eastern part. In the Island, the altitude to fluctuate in irregular pattern but the differences in height are unobservable since it runs gently, Tuti Island's surface is a flat with gentle slight slope, which runs from the north west to the south east, and as a result of that the main irrigation ditch was dug in the same direction. The annual flood frequently submerges the south eastern parts of the Island, which indicates that this area is the lower part of the Island. [Map No. (2)].

Considering the drainage, the rain water is generally logged in the low land in the middle of the Island, and it is difficult to be drained since the edges of the Island are surrounded by the dykes built to protect the Island from the annual flood.

Tuti Island Contour Map

Map No. (2)

3:3 Types of Soils

Soils in Tuti Island differ in characteristics, productivity, fertility and land use. As far as soil types are concerned, it is possible to identify four types of soil in the Island. [Map No. (3)].

3:3:1 Sand Soil:

This type of soil is mainly confined to the south eastern parts of the Island. These are of low fertility and thus, they have no value as far as agriculture is concerned. In the past there soils were left empty, but now a days, they are occupied by the expanding hum settlements.

3:3:2 Clay Soil:

The west and south-western parts of the Island are dominated by the clay soil which were deposited by the White Nile. These soils are of high fertility level, and consequently have a high productive capacity. So they have been used for vegetables and fruits production.

3:3:3 Silt Soil:

As a result of the annual Blue Nile flood, that usually submerges

Types of Soils in Tuti Island

Map No. (3)

The eastern, north eastern and the southern parts of the Island, these areas are covered by silt. Being of high fertility and high productive capacity, these areas have been used for fruit cultivation, but there are some tiny plots for vegetables production.

3:3:4 Old Clay Soil:

In the central parts of the Island the sedimentary rocks are covered with the old clay deposits. The soils here are less fertile and less productive, in some parts here the land to be rather salivated. This area is therefore occupied by old settlements.

3:4 Population:

3:4:1 Size & Growth:

Several times Tuti population has been enumerated e.g. 1956, 1973, 1983, 1988, 1991, and 1993.

Many population censuses were done or carried out in Tuti Island, such as the national population censuses of 1955, 1973 and 1983. In addition to these Hassan ⁽¹⁾made an enumeration of the residents of Tuti Island in 1963, also the Khartoum University Students and Graduates Association made another socioeconomic survey for the Island population in 1988. The population growth of Tuti Island is shown in Table (1).

Considering all these figures, it is possible to make some general statements about the population sized and growth in Tuti Island.

(1) In 1963 Hassan stated that the population in Tuti Island were about 3939 persons.

This figure means that, there was a sharp decrease in population number (about 32.7%) Hassan tried to attribute this decrease to

⁽¹⁾ Hassan, Omer B, 1963, Agriculture in Tuti Island B. A.

some factors he stated that, the high rate of immigration in 1955, the transfers of population, and the sampling techniques which was used in 1955 census, and based on a random sampling, are the main factors that explain the differences between the 1955 and 1963 figures.

- (2) The natural increase rates in the third world range between 2.0 and 3.5 percent per annum, a rate at which the population can more than double within the lifetime of generation (about 25 years)*. If we consider the Hassan's figure (3939) we can say that, it is what actually happened in Tuti Island as between 1963-1988, the population was doubled more than twice.

The population during the period 1955-1983 the growth rates were extremely low as in 1973 it was only 0.06%, and in 1983 it was only 0.96%. this low rates of growth can be attributed to the social and cultural habits and traditions, that is was well known in the past decade and earlier Tuti Island was a restricted area i.e. it was not permissible for the "strangers", or persons whose origin is not from Mahass⁽¹⁾ clan and not intermarried with Tuti people, to enter and live in Tuti Island and since the migration is considered as one of the major elements that lead to the population increase and growth, if we exclude this factor from influencing Tuti population, it may partly explain the low rates of growth of the Tuti population between 1955-1983, also these low rates may due to the low rates of fertility in Tuti Island.

* Dickenson, J. P. A Geography of the third world London, Methuen Co. 1983. P. 46.

⁽¹⁾ Sudanese Tribe in Northern Sudan.

Table (1): Population Growth and Structure in Tuti Island 1955 – 1988

Year	Total number	Male		Female		M / F ratio	Increase (percent)	Growth Rate
		Number	%	Number	%			
1955	5851	3220	55	2631	45	122.4%	-	-
1973	6515	3576	55	2939	45	121.7%	11.3	0.06
1983	7133	3795	53	3338	47	113.7%	9.5	0.96
1988	8429	4670	55	3759	45	124.2%	18.2	3.3

Sources: compiled by the author from the following sources:

- (1) Statistic department, national population census 1955.
- (2) Statistic department, national population census 1973.
- (3) Statistic department, national population census 1983.
- (4) Draft Report of Tuti Island population census 1988 by K. U. Students and Graduates Association in Tuti.

The period between 1983 and 1988 witnessed a very rapid population increase that the number increased from 7133 to 8424 with a period of only five years i.e. the growth rate increased from 0.96 to 3.3, which is an extremely high rate. However during this period. The Sudan as whole witnessed a serious natural disaster, particularly the 1984-1985 draught, this problem led a very high rate of Rural – Urban migration from the affected areas towards the capital Khartoum. And since those migrate seek for work and employment, some of them entered Tuti Island and involved into the agricultural activities as farmers or guards and some involved into the construction work as workers and some of them into the bricks-making work and other type of manual and physical works. However, as a result of the availability of the employment opportunities a large number of population entered the Island during the mid of 1980's. this can easily be imagined, if we know that, in 1963 the strangers were estimated to form not more than 7% while in 1988 census they form about 23% of the total population of Tuti Island. So this may explain the high population growth rate in Tuti Island in 1988.

3:4:2 Population Structure:

Hassan (1963) in his enumeration about the population in Tuti gave the following table.

Table (2):

Tuti Population by sex and age (1963)

Population Number			Age Groups							
			Under one year		1 – 5 years		5 – under puberty		Over puberty	
Total	Male	Female	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
3939	1956	1983	95	2.5	440	11	1203	30.5	2201	56

Source: Hassan, Omer B. "Agriculture in Tuti" (B. A), 1963.

It appears from table (2) that, the population of Tuti Island was rather young. For example, about 13.6% of the population were under 5 years of age, and 44% of the total population were under puberty.

The age structure may indicate that, the fertility must have been rather high at that period.

On the other hand, the 1988 census contains more detailed information about the age and sex structure. [Table No. (3)]. The table shows that.

Table No. (3)

Age structure of Tuti population (1988)

Age group	Total No.	Percentage
1 - 5	874	10.4
6 - 10	820	9.7
11 - 15	838	9.4
16 – 20	1090	12.9
21 – 25	1054	12.5
26 – 30	950	11.3
31 - 35	647	7.7
36 - 40	545	6.5
41 – 45	408	4.8
46 – 50	340	4.1
51 – 55	273	3.2
56 – 60	212	2.5
Above 60	377	4.5

Source: Unpublished draft of 1988 census, K. U. student and graduates association in Tuti Island.

About 10.4% of the total population (874) are under 5 years of age, and some 30% of the total population (2532) are under 15 years of age. If we

compare the population age structure of Tuti Island in 1963 to 1988, we can safely say that, the population of Tuti in 1988 is not as young as it were in 1963. Also the percentages of the population under 15 years of age in 1963 and 1988 form an indicator which provides us with some information about the birth rate during these periods. So it is possible to say that, the birth rate during 1960's and 1950's is higher than in 1970's and 1980's, that according to the percentage of the population under 15 years of age. This difference in birth rate can be attributed to the number of married persons in both periods, that in 1963 65% of the population over puberty age were got married, while in 1988 the married persons are only 40% of the adult population. And this is linked to social values, habits and traditions. While in the 1950's and in the 1980's and the 1970's its intensity highly declined and its influence was restricted.

Moreover, the economic conditions in the 1980's made it more difficult for people to get married or to maintain large families. Besides, prior to the 1980's, children used to help in agricultural activities, but nowadays, their economic participation highly reduced, where they have to be sent to schools.

As far as sex composition is concerned, we can single out that, in all these censuses the male ratio was higher than the female one.

As the male ratio range between 53 – 55 percent, while female ratio range between 45 – 47 percent. This can be noticed in all these censuses except 1963 one, in which the strangers had come from outside Tuti for work, males constituted the majority among them, so it would definitely affect the male/female ratio if we exclude them and this what was actually happened. As far as those migrants are concerned, and according to the 1988 census, about 72% of them are males, while females constitute only 28%. Figure (2).

3:4:3 The Ethnic Structure:

Tuti residents can be considered as one large family which descendant of the Mahass tribe of the Northern Sudan, that settled in Tuti Island during the 15th and the 16th centuries. As a result the social structure seems to be very homogenous.

Tuti population can be divided into the following groups on the basis of origin and tribal structure:-

A. Islanders:

- (i) **Mahas:** This is the predominant group and it is composed of 15 major families as a sub tribal groups, these are the following:-

1- Aboudia	6- Ghardugab	11- Mriomab
2- Amarab	7- Hussienab	12- Onab
3- Awamra	8- Khogalab	13- Saadallab
4- Baloulab	9- Kunus	14- Shakertab
5- Daleelab	10- Meknab	15- Shawishab ⁽¹⁾

These families in the past formed the most important social institutions, and to make-decision on any issue each family should have to be represented. Also these families were well known among the Islanders that everyone can easily classify himself to his family which, had its own district the Island. But recently these families in situations became less important and were replaced by several substitute social institutions such as clubs, youth societies. Also most of these families were intermingled with each other through

⁽¹⁾ Hill, L. (1965) The Tuti community.

intermarriage, and finally the districts mixed as these families grew larger very rapidly, so they were scattered in the different new extensions of the old settlements.

(ii) Non Mahas:

This group consists of those people who are not Mahas and who had settled in Tuti several generation ago. The largest of these was of an Egyptians origins. These are the Abu-Adil, el-Agib and Khatab families.

Recently these people have been assimilated into the community via intermarriage with the Mahas clan.

B. Out siders "strangers":-

The term "stranger" in Tuti Island refers to the persons whose origin is not Tuti i.e. he is not Mahas and he had no marriage relationship with the Mahas clan. These groups come to Tuti mainly for work. They include:-

(i) NUBA:

Who work as house-servents, their number is too small.

(ii) SOUTHERS:

Who were employed as a construction workers, mainly from Nuer and Shuluk tribes, also their number is small.

(iii) ARAB:

Arab refers to those from the Kubabiesh and Hassanya tribes. They are mainly involve in brick work as labourer, or as cart – driver. Their number is larger than previous two groups.

(iv) WESTERNERS

Some of them from Kordufan, but most of them are mainly from Darfur region and they involve largely in agricultural activities as farmers or guards.

They constitute the largest group of the out siders.

Despite the long time these groups have been working in Tuti Island, they are not yet fully accepted by the Islanders, as they have no any marriage relationship with the Islanders, and they still live in the fields in small huts.

3.5 Labour Force:

So as to measure the labour force in Tuti Island, both Hassan (1963) and 1988 census, used the "gainful worker" approach. In this approach the enumerator asks each person about big gainful occupation. In this case, the persons who are no longer actively employed or looking for work, such as pensioners and remittances receivers will be included in the labour force. Also those looking for jobs for the first time will be included in the labour force. This is so because the "gainful work" approach is not restricted to a specific period of time i.e. it gives no regard to when the work was exactly done⁽¹⁾.

In 1963: Hassan stated that all persons who were gainfully employed, or were actively engaged in economic activities were 1231 persons or about 29% of the total population in Tuti Island. The 1988 census, on the other hand, indicates that, the gainfully employed people are 2972 persons or some 35% of the total population of Tuti Island.

⁽¹⁾ Galal – el-Din, M. A. Population and labour force in the Sudan, An introduction to the Sudan economy edi. 1975. K.U.R.

Also according to 1988 census, there are 5457 persons, whose main occupation or activities are not economic (mainly students and household duties), who have subsidiary economic occupation. Despite this students can be considered as a potential labour force since they can – by way or another – participate in the economic activities. So if we add the students to the economically active population, the labour force proportion would rise from 35% to 65% which is an extremely high proportion.

As for the distribution of the labour force by occupation, we can say that, there are no real differences between the situation in 1963 and 1988 (see table [4]). Those who were classified as farmers in 1963 and 1988 were respectively 33% and 34% of the working population.

**Table (4): Distribution of the labour force by occupation
1963 and 1988**

Year \ Occup.	Famer		Govt. employee		Worker		Others		Total
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	
1963 ⁽¹⁾	404	33	413	33.5	350	28.5	64	5	1231
1988 ⁽²⁾	1024	34	940	31.6	604	20.3	404	13.6	2972

Sources: (1) Hassan, Omer B. Agriculture in Tuti 1963.

(2) The draft report of 1988 census.

Those engaged in governmental services constitute 33.5% in 1963 census compared to 31.6% in 1988. The manual worker slightly decreased, as their ratio was 28.5% in 1963, but in 1988 that ratio dropped to 20.3% of the labour force.

This may be due to the high percentage of the educated people in Tuti Island, who usually tend to refuse the physical and manual jobs.

In contrast, the number of the people who engage in other types of occupation markedly increase, as their ratio in 1963 was only 5%, but in 1988 it increased to 13.6%.

This can be attributed to the fact that, during last decade the attraction of the civil service highly decreased, since it does not respond the employee's basic need, as its salary rarely covers the life's running costs. As a result of this a large number of people tend to leave the civil service and seek for other type of work in which they can gain more money such as middleman, or involve in the commercial work. Also this group includes most of the student who had complete their education, and they did not find a job yet. [Figure (13)].

So all those people lead to the marked increase in the ratio of people who involve in other types of work in 1988.

3: 6 Education:

Historically, Tuti was known as one of the most ancient and important centres for religious teaching since the middle of the 16th century, certainly some prominent holy men had taught in Tuti Island at various historical periods such as sheikh Arbab El-Agayeed, K sheikh Hamad wad Un Meryoum, and sheikh Khogli Abu-El-jaz. So since those early days, the "Koran-fire" never faded away, and the old mosque played a significant role in teaching people the principle of the Islam, as well as, how to read and write in "Khalwa", (Koranic schools).

Formal education, on the other hand, started in Tuti Island early this century. The first elementary school for boys was opened in 1917 with four teachers^{*}. As a result of its continuous successes in the educational

^{*} Personal interviews.

processes, the "Khalwa attraction began to decrease. By 1947 the "Khalwa" was closed and disappeared. With the establishment of Tuti Development Company in 1946 and the development of the national movement in the late 1940's, the rush towards education increased. Despite the fact that, female education was logging behind the male education, by the 1940's a home class room for girls and women was established and run by some educated girls in Tuti Island. By 1952 an elementary school for girls was opened. Also by the beginning of the 1970's the primary school's capacity for both boys and girls was doubled, i.e. each school contained 12 class rooms with a full capacity of about 600 pupils for each school.

In 1969, an intermediate school for boys was established, followed in 1975 by an intermediates school for girls.

The latest achievement in the field of education in Tuti Island, was the establishment of Tuti high secondary school for girls, which was established in 1984.

It is important to mention that, most of these schools were built through the self-help efforts, and the governmental support was generally limited.

Now a days, the majority of the Tuti students are receiving their education within the Island, except those boys of secondary and post-secondary school education, who are receiving their education outside the Island.

According to Hassan (1963), the number of the illiterate population ... was: about 1783 persons or about 45.3% of the total population, while the educated people were estimated to be about 2156 persons or about 54.7% of the total population.

No doubt, the ratio of the educated people was relatively high at that time compared to the rest of the country. However, during the 1970's effective efforts were exerted so as to reduce the percentage of the illiteracy, by establishing evening schools for adult education. These efforts combined with the formal education were very fruitful, as their results were revealed

in the 1988 census. According to that census, the total number of illiterate population in Tuti Island was 831 persons or about 11.3% of the total population, which is an extremely small ratio compared to the Sudan's illiteracy level which is more than 80%.

Moreover, among the total population the students form about 30% in 1988 compared to 14.3% of the total population in 1963.

From the distribution of population by the education level attained, which is shown in table (5), it is clear that, elementary education is the most widespread representing 32.9% of the educated population, followed by the secondary 27.7%, intermediate 20.2%, higher education 10.3% and the non-formal education which is representing 8.9%.

Table (5):

Distribution of population by level of education in Tuti Island (1988)

Level	Non-formal.	Elem.	Inter.	Second.	Higher	Total
Number	584	2171	1331	1827	681	6594
%	8.9	32.9	20.2	27.7	10.3	100

Source: Draft report of 1988 census.

One of the benefits of the high education ratio in Tuti Island is the large number of Tuti people who occupy governmental posts outside the Island. Some in the ministries and corporations, a large number of school teachers, and some of them are university lecturers. The majority, however, holds minor posts such as clerks and accountants. Also the distribution of the labour force by occupation reflects that about 32% of them are working as a governmental employee which is a high ratio.

Chapter Four

Community development projects

in Tuti Island

[The Case Study of Tuti Development Company]

Chapter Four

4:1 Historical Background

In 1944, the soil conservation committee recommended that, 350 feddans of Tuti land must be taken for the benefits of the Sudan Government, so as to provide experimental farm for the school of agriculture. To implement this decision the committee advised to purchase the Island and resettle the residents elsewhere⁽¹⁾. The government decided to expropriate the Island as the simplest method of implementing its plan. The inhabitants of Tuti, on the other hand, were strongly opposed to this scheme. They refused to leave the Island and they maintained that if any development is to be undertaken in Tuti, they were only the people who had the right to undertake it. However, the government refused this and insisted on the expropriation of the Island. Riot started against the government, and people clashed with the police, and one Islander was killed.*

The Tuti defiance of the government was widely upheld and sustained until the government scheme was cancelled⁽²⁾.

The people of Tuti were not satisfied by the cancellation of the government plan, but also they designed a comprehensive plan to establish a cooperative company to be financed by the Islanders and its prime objective was to close the way for any new attempts to expropriate the land. The idea of the company was well reviewed by the Islanders, and highly supported, that the entire population insisted to participate in the company establishing. Some men sold even their wife's jewellery, and ornaments so

⁽¹⁾ Sudan Govern., soil conservation committee annual report 1944.

* Ahmed Mohammed Yousif.

⁽²⁾ Khaliefa, Ameen M. Tuti the struggler, Khartoum, Arabic publisher, 1983, (in Arabic).

as to participate. It was nothing important for them but their Island and entity. The company was called Tuti Development Company, and the capital raised was L.S 10,000 divided into 1000 ordinary shares of L.S. 10. The company was registered according to the Companies Ordinance of 1925, in February, 1946.

A board of directors was elected to run the company. The board contacted the governmental departments for the technical assistance, and it was provided with the three necessary man power, and professionals to help in land registration procedures and to carry out a land survey for the agricultural land and to decide the location of the pump, canal, and roads within the fields. All members agreed to grant tiny pieces of land for the company so as to dig the main canal. The canal was two meters wide, and with four meters on each side as a road, i.e. ten meters were devoted to the canal. The canal was dug around the village with length of 6 kilometers. (See map 4).

Also the pump site was demarcated in the highest place in the field [see plate (1) and (2)]. Moreover, the land of the canal was registered as a property for the company.

4:2 The Company's objectives:

The central objectives which were agreed upon for Tuti development company can be summarized as follows:-

- (a) To supply water for irrigation.
- (b) To initiate new enterprises in the Island such as a dairy farm, poultry farm, and any other businesses associated with farming and which may be advantageously carried along the cooperative's principles.
- (c) To establish shops for the distribution and marketing of the farm products (dairy produce, poultry, eggs ... etc). And to control all the trade to, from and in the Island.

- (d) To improve farming practices and increase agricultural production by selling and distributing the manures (artificial or natural), implements, machinery, and other agricultural inputs, as well as increasing the area under cultivation, increasing with horticultural production.
- (e) To advance and rent credit to farmers, tenants and others who may be willing to cultivate or improve any land in which the company is interested.
- (f) To take part in or cooperate with any company, cooperative or person undertaking agricultural activities and with similar objectives to those of the company.
- (g) To invest in any income, that generating from the company activities, properly to provide the Island with the necessary social services⁽¹⁾.

4:3 The Administration system:

The company has its general assembly, which consists of all the shareholders. It holds at least one meeting annually to check the financial and administrative performance, and to elect the new board of directors. The financial report has to be checked by a certified accountant.

However, the number of the board of director initially proposed was 20 members, but latter it was reduced to 12 members, and now there are no more than 8 members. The board is structured as follows: the chairman, general secretary, the secretary of financial affairs, the scheme director, the director of the buses (now cancelled), the farmer representatives (two farmers), and the rest person as members in the board. All these persons work as a volunteers, that they are not paid for this work. However, the

⁽¹⁾ Memorandum and articles of association of Tuti development company 1946.

board is helped by some salaried persons, those persons are, the accountant two guards for the canal, 'Nazir" to organize the irrigation process farmers and to collect the money, a pump driver and technician for the pump.

Map (4)

Agriculture and type of irrigation in Tuti Island 1963

4:4 Achievements

4:4:1 River transport:

In 1946, as an experiment the company decided to enter the field of river transport.

It succeeded to obtain the bid offered by the government for the sailing boat connecting the Island with Khartoum and Omdurman. The reasons for undertaking this job were:

- (a) To ease the difficulties suffered by the Island population especially of irregularity and delay caused to those working outside the Island;
- (b) To ease the transportation of farm products, that were daily transported to the Khartoum central market, and
- (c) Such a work may lead to a direct financial benefits for the company⁽¹⁾.

However, in the first year the company got profits of about 216 pounds⁽²⁾.

When time passed the company developed the sailing boats in steamers.

The company continued in winning the bids until 1950 when the river transport department brought a new ferry.

4:4:2 The Agricultural Scheme:

⁽¹⁾ Tuti Development Company, annual report, 1947.

⁽²⁾ Ibid.

The agricultural scheme is one of the most prominent achievement which was done by the company. Agriculture – all that time – constituted the backbone of the economic activities in the Island since nearly all of the Islanders depended on it.

There were some reasons that made the company put concentrate on agriculture. First, nearly all of Tuti lands are highly fertile. Second, irrigation water is available. And third, the capital Khartoum with its increasing population and demand for fruits and vegetable will form a suitable market for the Island production.

The company plan, in this field, had two legs, to increase the production of vegetables, and to introduce some new crops.

In past the Islanders used to irrigate their crops by traditional and manual method of irrigation in the sense that they used sagia and shadoaf.

The first diesel pump was installed in 1916 by the agriculture department, but the scheme was collapsed and no farmer was willing to give land for canal.

Also in the periods 1925-1926 and 1930-1935 there were attempts to install pumps, but none of them succeeded. There was always a dispute between the pump owner and the farmers on water prices. So farmers tend to irrigate their farms by sagia and shadoof, both were labor demanding and of limited capacity. As a result small areas were under cultivation.

The farmers in the Island used to grow vegetables such as cress, tomatoes, potatoes, cucumber, okra, onions and jew's mallow. [plate (3)]. These vegetables were grown in ting plots as a result of the small amount of water available.

The company to solve the irrigation water problem brought a small diesel pump with (10") diameter in 1947, and later in 1949 alarger diesel pump with a (16") diameter was installed.

Before the company, the irrigation water was the critical problem, and the production hardly exceed local needs. But as soon as the pumps were installed there were radical changes in life of the formers and community as whole. As water was made available, every farmer had the chance to increase the acreage under cultivation which – no doubt- meant an increase in the farmers' incomes, and the reduction of the manual and physical efforts, that were exerted before the company, way an important change. The farmer and his family used to spend nearly all day in the field, especially for irrigation, but when the ditich was dug and water flew through the farms, only one or two men were quite enough to follow up the irrigation process. As a result children were gradually relieved from the agricultural work, and the most important thing was that most of them were sent to school. From that date on education became more and more valued by parents and this may-partly- explain the high proportion of the educated people in the Island.

Two or three years passed, and all people felt the changes in their life. Vegetables were been grown in large areas, and considerable quantities of surplus was available for marketing.

The company gained the confidence of the farmers, so they used to seek advice concern atering, seed selection ... etc.

However, the board of directors, here, decided to fulfil the second part of its plan, i.e. to introduce new crops, particularly, fruit trees.

It was too difficult at beginning to convince farmers to leave their traditional type of agriculture and turn to new types of crops such as fruit trees which longer time and more are until the mature stage compared to vegetables which can be harvested two or three times within one month. But the company pushed the matter forward when it announced that all fruit trees were to be irrigated free of charge for a given period, and for the

half the normal charge until it become fruitful, in order to encourage farmers to grow the fruit trees.

So, in 1949 – 1950 the first fruit garden was planted, and then the number of the fruit gardens began to increase gradually. The number of the fruit gardens shot up sharply after the first fruit farm was harvested, and its products were sold.

At first fruits were restricted in the time tree [plate (4)], but by 1955 other types of fruit trees were introduced such as Mango, Orange, Grape fruits and Guafa. In addition to the fruit trees, clover also was introduced at the same time as fodder, and a cash crop as well.

Vegetables production continued in the farms but their acreages were reduced as a result of the introduction of the fruit trees. As a result of the high profit, from fruit production, the area under fruit gardens was doubled several times until it reached 750 feddans or 83% of the total arable area of Tuti Island. [map (4)].

Life in Tuti Island experienced an enormous change both socially and economically, and despite the absence of the necessary statistical data. Which could have enabled us to make a comparison between the economic status before and after the company establishment, there are sufficient indicators of socio-economic advancement within the Island community. For example, during the early 1950's there was a rush towards construction, and the settlement area expanded considerably. Also most of Tuti people began to rebuild their houses using red bricks and some using cement, instead of mud and local materials, which indicates the development that took place in the social life. Moreover, in the education field we find that, the elementary school for girls was built in 1952, and the elementary school for boys was rebuild in 1956. Also during the 1950's many social institutions were built. That in 1955 the labourer's club was founded and in 1957 it was followed by "el-ttawn" sport club. Also the old mosque in 1959

was rebuilt in its present design. Moreover the clinic, which had built in 1930 – was developed in to a sanitation centre in 1957 with a modern building suitable for this stage. During the 1960's the married population proportion highly increased.

Hassan (1963) stated that at 65% of the Island population were got married. All these indicators give us a sufficient information about the socio-economic advancement in Tuti Island after the establishment to Tuti Development Company, particularly if we knew that nearly all of these achievements were realized through self-help efforts.

4:4:3 In-land transport:

The distance between the village and the Khartoum ferry is about two kilometers, until 1956 the company bought abuse so as to transport people between the ferry and the village. This has solved the problem for the Islanders in the beginning, as time passed and population increased the single bus was not enough and two more buses were brought by Tuti Development Company in 1965. In fact, in addition to their services for the Island, the buses were very profitable to the extent that they used to compensate for pump's losses, which was very frequent, as they rarely covered their running costs.

These buses continued to work until 1979 when they were sold by the company and that was because:-

- (a) They were too old.
- (b) New buses were brought by Tuti people council as a branch of the Khartoum transport company.
- (c) The chronic fuel crises at that time.
- (d) They were sold to cover the costs of the electrification of the agricultural scheme.

4:4:4 Electrification of Agricultural Scheme:

A further development in the company's work took place in 1977, when diesel pumps were electrified. As a result of the rapid increase of the cultivated area, water became insufficient for the irrigation, especially fruits which require large amount of water, and also vegetables which require frequent watering with very short intervals. Therefore, the diesel pumps had to work for longer hours, and this was hampered by chronic shortage of fuel.

So to solve this chain of problems the board of director decided to electrify the pump.

However, the results of the pump electrification revealed in the consequent years, that the revenue began to increase compared to the pre-electrification years. [figure no. (5)] [in next chapter].

In addition to these major achievements, the company has a contribution in the other aspects of life, for example, the company sometimes contributed to build schools or rebuilding them, or the sanitation cont ... etc.

Also in 1976, the company tried to take responsibility of the river transport between Tuti and capital Khartoum – Bantoons (Ferry) – but the river transport department refused this and preferred to keep it under the public sector control.

Moreover, the company considering the situation of poor farmers, it used to supply them with water at the half price, and sometimes free of charge.

On the field of the environmental health, the company since it started and until the early 1970's used to sprinkle the farms by insecticides, so as to reduce the probabilities of pests diseases incidence.

4:5 Constraints to the Company:

It is well known that, one of the main essential and fundamental factors, which lead to success of any program or project, are the well-defined planning, which determines what exactly is needed, and how these needs can be obtained.

Also the follow up of the implementation stage is necessary for any project.

However, Tuti Development Company faces many problems, which can be summarized as follows:-

4:5:1 Administration:

Administration plays an important role in realizing the stated objectives of any project, and any failure in the administration aspects would definitely lead to the failure of the whole project. So administration can be considered as a backbone for any project or program.

As far as Tuti development is concerned, we can safely say that administration constitutes the major and prime obstacle, which retards the progress of the company. The problems in the company include:-

- (1) The non-professional administration that means the board of directors is a group of volunteers, so they have their own jobs, which take most of their time. One consequence of this type of administration is that after the election we can hardly find the whole board working together as a one body, and most of the activities are left –usually- to one or two persons to deal with. As a result of these administrative problems, the company turned to be a mere land lord selling water for irrigation. Even this task is hardly performed satisfactorily and water charges are rarely collected in full.
- (2) Also administration negatively affects the financial performance of the company. The delay in collecting the irrigation water charges

lead to the delay of the budget which force the tax department to impose an estimated figure for the company taxes regardless of the company losses. [Table No. (6)].

Table No. (6):

Losses and taxes imposed to the company

Year	The Net losses	Imposed taxes
1980	2.007	6.189
1981	6.604	10.636
1982	1.203	9.850
1983	3.310	13.700

- (3) Also there is a weakness in the regulations that govern the water distribution among the farm because of the absence of the strong administration and the company staff does not work on fulltime basis, so some farmers may break the regulation and irrigate their farms before their scheduled irrigation time.
- (4) Also the irrigation water of the company is quite cheap compared with private pumps, that in pas the private pump owner irrigate for other former for one third ($\frac{1}{3}$) of the crop, but latter this agreement was modified, and the farmer buy water from the private pump owner by the hour of supply. One of the obvious consequences of the cheap price of the company water is that, whenever the company irrigation water is available, all farmers a bandon the private pumps supply, and even the private pump owners abandon their pumps and depend on the company's water supply. Private pumps irrigate on area of one feddans of fruit trees for about L.S 250, while the

company price is about L.S 50⁽¹⁾ i.e. the company price equals 20% of private pumps price. This costed the company huge losses and its revenues rarely cover its running costs, which is compensated for from the busses' revenues. As a result, sometimes, it is difficult for the company to pay its growing debts to the national electricity corporation, and this threatens the continuity of electricity of supply and ultimately irrigation water.

But we can also say that this chain of problems can easily be solved if a professional administration is available.

4:5:2 The Siltation Problem:

When the pump site was demarcated many considerations were made, such as the altitude, gradient, and the distance of the pump site from the Nile. But in the 1960's, there was a large accumulation of deposits on the northern end of the Island. And as a result of silt accumulation the pump's site now is separated from the Nile course by about 90 meters, [plate (5)].

So the pump is now far from river, which means the stoppage of water supply. To solve this problem a wide canal was dug to permit water to pass to the pump site. But with the annual Nile flood and disposition, the canal level became higher than the river level, and flow of water was blocked again. This problem is solved annually and partially by redigging the canal after the flood season. But this is money and time consuming. The most recent attempt to solve this problem was done by installing one of the two scheme's pumps near the Nile course, so as to fill the canal, [plate 6] and then water is pumped to the fields by the other pump. But such an experiment did not solve the problem, but it caused a new problem

⁽¹⁾ Interviews with formers.

by cutting the irrigation capacity by 50% as it relies on one pump for irrigation at present.

The reduction of the quantities of water available for irrigation made it insufficient for all farmers, as it now takes 28 – 30 days to irrigate the whole area of the scheme instead of 15 days required in the past.

As a result 5 farms located at the extreme southern side suffer continuous water shortages, [plate (7)]. So to deal with such a problem, many farmers bought their own private pumps to use to irrigate their crops whenever there is a problem with company's water supply [plate(8)].

Plate (5): The Nile Course is far away from the pump site.

Plate (6): Two big pumps in the Scheme working at 50% capacity.

Plate (7): Shortage of irrigation means fruit trees fading and withering

Plate (8): Private pumps were brought to work during periods of water shortages

Now, there are 27 private pumps in the area traditionally irrigated by company's pumps [map (15)]. The siltation problem can be solved by

changing the pump site north ward to be close to the Nile course, and the area between the new site and the old one (about 90 meters) has to be linked by a large pump to link the pump with the main irrigation canal, this can allow company to operate in full capacity, i.e. the two pump, (10" – 10") can pump water for irrigation.

4:4:3 Political Conflicts

Despite of the unique unity among the population of Tuti Island, which started with the defiance of the colonial government in 1946 and led to the establishment of Tuti Development Company, many conflicts often occur. One example was in 1957, when all of Tuti community was divided into two groups mainly for some political reasons. Tuti Development Company was highly effected by that events when the board of directors was also divided into two groups, and one group of Tuti development shareholders tried to sell their shares through courts to cause the company to collapse. The other group did their best to buy all shares that were for sale to keep company a float.

During the establishment stage, no one was allowed to have more than 5 shares so as to give the chance for the maximum number of people to participate, but as a result of this conflicts, shares were accumulated in few hands. Some people now have more than 50 shares, most of them were belonged to one large family in the Island. So some people believe that the company became a property of this family rather than the entire community, and consequently the company lost a lot of the acceptance which it had received earlier.

These conflict continued when those who left the company bought a bus only to compete with the company, despite the fact that in that time there was not a demand for more than one bus.

However, this was stopped in 1958, when the first military government abolished political parties. So the company began to re-gain the confidence

and began functioning again, though not as strong as before, as shares were accumulated in few hands compared with the early stage of the company.

4:5:4 Other Problems:

Traditionally agriculture in Tuti Island associated with simple and traditional tools and techniques, which depend mainly on the physical and manual efforts such as spade, 'saluka', sickle, hoes and other hand tools. Also a draught animal and small metal plough are used for ploughing. However these traditional hand tools have some advantages e.g. these tools characterized by low cost since they do not need more than some manual effort, which is low and cheap compared to the advanced and modern technology. Also these tools usually do a very compared with modern technology.

Note withstanding these advantages, the main problem which stems out from using these simple tools is that, they responsible-to a great extent, for the low productivity of the land and retard the large-scale agriculture – so, by way or another, these tools effect the income and level of living of the local farmers.

The technological problem can be solved through the introduction and implementation of the modern and advanced technology. But this step is – also – hampered by the another problem, which is the extensive land fragmentation in Tuti Island , as Tuti Island is divided into 88 unequal land units (sagia) and each (sagia) is further subdivided into ten to thirty narrow strips (habil)⁽¹⁾. As this divisions had taken place since earlier times, so several generations in hereted these holdings. This had led to an extensive fragmentation of land and fragmentation of cultivation units, as habil can be considered as the smallest workable plot. In Tuti Island the average area

⁽¹⁾ Tuti Development Company documents.

of the holdings is about 2 feddans and less, such a fragmentation made the introduction of modern technology very difficult e.g. the modern techniques of ploughing. This is that because, there are different types of crops which need different type of horticultural practices.

Also the price fluctuation constitutes a major problem which face the farmers in Tuti Island. This problem became more serious since the farmers in Tuti used to cultivate some fruits which are very changeable in demand and market e.g. lime in sometimes (Ramadan) becomes very popular and its price shoots up sharply and doubled several time and vice-versa. The problem is generally enhanced by farmers themselves as they used to deal in their crops after harvesting as an individuals, regardless to the prices.

However, this problem can be solved through the monopoly of the trade of all crops that cultivated in Tuti Island by the Tuti Development Company. The monopoly of these crops and their trade will-no doubt- to a pattern of stability in prices, as the company can control the market and demand and seek for the highest price for these crops for the benefits of the local farmers and this job had already stated among the company objectives.

Moreover, the limitation of capital also constitutes a problem for both the company and the farmer, and it is the main problem which retards the progress of the company's work and prevents the creation and initiation of any new works or activities for the benefits of the entire community.

And, finally despite of problems of old equipment, capital, fragmentation of land, and price fluctuation, the farmer in Tuti Island was put into unbalanced competition with farmers from other cities and villages around the Capital Khartoum such as Suba, elJaylee and elKadaroo, where the farmers are working in large schemes or farms either under the public or private sector control, with much more facilities e.g. large-scale agriculture is practiced, modern technology is used and in most case, these farms or schemes with such facilities used to produce different types of crops, but

they characterized by more quantity and high quality, which is an unbalanced competition, if we bear in mind, the conditions under which the farmer in Tuti Island is working.

Chapter Five

Evaluation & Future Prospects

Chapter Five

5:1 Evaluation

Ekong (1983) discusses the importance of the evaluation stage for any C.D. efforts, indicating that there is more emphasis placed on the approaches and strategies than on the evaluation of the end results, he elaborates that the "right" approach does not mean the success of the community development efforts, he gives more details when he says (a community development may succeed in meeting its pre-defined objectives, but it may fail in not participating the related change or effect which its success had introduced. Also a community development program may fail to attain its stated objectives, but may succeed in other directions)⁽¹⁾.

So the evaluation of any community development program is very important not only in determining areas of success and fail, but also in the unanticipated effects which success or failure may have introduced.

As far as Tuti Development Company is concerned, we can identify that, the phases and the steps for the community development, which were stated by Taylor and Hays⁽²⁾, were typically followed at the establishment stage of Tuti Development Company, as needs were identified, physical resources were harnessed, technical assistance is brought, objectives were determined ... etc.

Concerning the community participation, at the initial stage, all population of the Island were involved in Decision – making process, but later on the decision – making process was organized to be made through the board of directors and the general assembly, the later one is considered as the highest level of decision-making. Also the implementation stage reflects

⁽¹⁾ Ekong, E. Ekong, success and failure in C.D efforts C. D. Journal Vol. 12, No. 3 , 1983.

⁽²⁾ See chapter (2), pp 7-8/

a type of community participation in the first stages of the company establishment. Moreover, the benefits are generally distributed among the members of the society particularly the social services. On the other hand the financial profits used to be distributed among the shareholders. But the most prominent benefits are the public services e.g. buses, river transport and fruit gardens. Another contribution of the company was the increasing of the ratio of the educated people.

The evaluation stage or process is done by the annually through the general assembly which its main function is to check the performance of the company.

All these kinds of participation were implemented perfectly in the past when the company had an effective administrative system, where the annual general assembly used to be held for following up the performance, but nowadays, this is absent, as the assembly is rarely held, and moreover the benefits were highly reduced, the company hardly covers its running cost since the company lost its way of multi-dimensional activities, that it is working in irrigation only, so the services were stopped as well as the profits. Another factor made the community participation be restricted recently, which is accumulation of shares in a very few hands.

In the socio-economic aspects, we can identify that the company had achieved a lot for the Island community, where it accomplished the river transport, the agricultural scheme, and the Island transport. All these works were led to a better level of living condition and social services for the entire community. Moreover, the outstanding feature in these aspects is the principle, which governs the company's achievement, is that the company was established based on no profit no loss for its members, and its main goal is not profit maximization, but maximization of the satisfaction and welfare of the entire community of the Island.

Note withstanding, all above achievements, the company has got some a disadvantages.

One disadvantage is the administration, which retards the progress of the company.

We can imagine the administrative defect knowing that, the area under cultivation, which belongs to the company, was reduced from 750 feddans to about 350 feddans. About 53% and main canal was reduced to half-length (from 6 kilometers to 3 kilometers). This reduction is result⁶ed mainly from the expansion of the settlement area, such a remarked reduction should be followed by an efficient water supply for the small area [map (5)], also such a reduction should reduce the irrigation burden on the company, which enables it to create and initiate a new series of work. But this did not happen, as company's activity was restricted in single dimension i.e. the irrigation field, and even in this field the company did not manage to supply all farms with sufficient water, and as a result there are 27 private pumps in work – nowadays, in the area which is traditionally irrigated by the company. These pumps work whenever there is shortage in water supply. So all these defect can be solved easily through efficient and effective administration.

In the field of the financial performance, the company had got high profits in the early time or after establishment, but since the 1970's there was a pattern of fluctuation between profits and losses, but by end of the 1979 there were a continuous losses as a result of the baying of the buses and the company became dependent on the pumps [figure 4]. [Table (7)]. But most of these losses can be avoided or reduced at least, through some administrative control, as most of these losses were stem from the estimated taxes which imposed on the company as a result of the budget delaying.

The pumps of the company began with considerable profits at earlier times. But with the introduction of the fruit gardens, the cultivated area, and the demand for water supply were increased, also the fuel prices during 1970's were doubled several times while the price of irrigation was increased in a very low rate compared with the first one, all these factors led the pumps to get losses, but these losses were generally compensated by the buses-earnings which were normally get high profits. In 1979 the buses were sold and with their money, the electrification of the pumps was achieved. So as a result of the electrification the pumps began to get profits, despite the fact that the water prices were few. Figure (5) shows the pumps budget 1972 – 1984; from the figure, we can conclude that during the period 1972 – 1975 flood damages the pump had some losses. However, from 1978 – 81.

The budget of Tuti Development Company 1971 – 1984

Year	General			The Buses		The Pumps	
	Revenue	Expenditure	Difference	Revenue	Expenditure	Revenue	Expenditure
71 - 72	7692	8352	659	3801	2383	3890	2291
72 - 73	8394	8848	453	4123	2222	4271	3567
73 - 74	9376	8508	467	4499	2184	4876	3586
74 - 75	12495	11680	815	5573	3537	6808	5689
75 - 76	12129	12362	233	6742	4820	5377	5612
76 - 77	12676	14523	1846	7221	7658	5377	4972
77 - 78	12294	12176	117	5088	6270	7185	3449
78 - 79	13488	7800	5688	-	-	7434	2799
79 - 80	9492	10036	1543	-	392	9492	3234
80 - 81	10665	12672	2007	-	-	10665	2961
81 - 82	9988	16593	6604	-	-	9988	11531
82 - 83	15803	17006	1203	-	-	15803	12019
83 - 84	30146	33456	3310	-	-	30146	27118

* Source: Tuti Development Company annual reports 1971 – 1984.

(1) Figures are in Sudanese pounds.

The pumps gained high profits because of the electrification, again in 1982-84 the pumps began to loss because of the low prices of the irrigation water as it do not compensate the electricity prices. [Figure 5].

In addition, the buses financial performance, as shown in figure (6), is quite clear that, they used to earn profits. In addition to their services for the community the buses used to get high profits, as they used to cover the running costs of the whole company, also from the figure we can easily noticed that the buses during 1972 – 1984 were very profitable despite the fact that they were very old and this may indicated that the buses were not profitable as earlier when they were in a good situation.

5:2 Future Prospects

As far as future prospects of Tuti Development Company are concerned, I prefer that, Tuti Development company, to be converted into a cooperative society, and I believe that if there was a choice for the people when the company was established, the people of Tuti would no doubt chose the cooperative sector to includes their company, but the cooperative ordinance was issued in 1948 while the company was established in 1946. However, the cooperative sector is preferable for many reasons:-

- (1) In companies, there is a high consideration for the number of the shares, as the persons who have large number of shares can dominate the assembly procedures. In contrast, the Cooperative Act states that, every member has one vote, regardless of the number of shares and no one can hold more than it can.
- (2) The cooperative sector has an exemption from taxes of the profits, but one the other hand taxes and duties form a heavy burden on the company's budget, and this exactly what is happening with Tuti Development company.

- (3) The cooperative Act does not tend to the matter of profitability in the first place, as this sector is tends to maximization of the social benefits.
- (4) Moreover, the Cooperative Act states that, a ratio of the net profit has to be devoted to the social services in the area of the society.
- (5) The cooperative society characterized by unlimited capital, while the company's ordinances determines that every company should be established with a limited capital.

All these characteristics of the cooperative sector make it reasonable to support the idea of converting Tuti Development Company into a cooperative one.

This process can be achieved as follows, assessing all the property of the company e.g., land, pumps ... etc. Then re-evaluating all these properties, and consequently, re-estimating the initial capital for the company according to its property's prices or value. And the initial 1000 shares can be divided into 10,000 or more according to the estimated capital.

No doubt the one share of L.S 10 at the 1950's may be evaluated to equal e3.g. L.S. 100. So a one who has one share in 1950's may own 10 shares according the recent capital.

If this is done, the shareholders who own a large number of shares have to be convinced to sale some shares for the persons who have a desire to participate.

There are two basic functions for this process first to distribute the shares, which means more support and more participation, and second, such a process will increase the capital for the company to create and initial new series of projects.

Moreover, the company is in a great need for an efficient and professional board of directors for the administrative affairs or at least a professional director or manager.

In addition, the board of directors has to be supported by some educated youth, to help in administration.

Tuti Development company has a complete infrastructures that needed for any scheme, e.g. a good canal, roads on both sides of the canal, two large pump ... etc. so the company has a well-established base and chance to carry out any sort of development, and the most easiest one is to control the fruit trade in and outside the Island for the benefit of the local people.

However, it is easy to state any number of objectives, but the most important is the achievements. The initial objectives of the company can be considered as the most suitable objectives to begin with, no doubt, they may need some modifications.

The most important thing to be beard in mind is that, the central objective of such a company must not be the profits, but the maximization of the welfare of the whole community of Tuti Island.

Moreover, if these problems, which were stated earlier, are solved, Tuti Development company will has a prosper future as far as community development is concerned.

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